

SIGNIFICANCE OF ONLINE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article is dedicated to “Significance of online education in Uzbekistan”. It demonstrates that the importance of online learning for English language learners. Distance education is different from the traditional education. And its educational information and instruction is taught to learners who are physically distant from the source of that information and instruction.*

Keywords: *online education, distance learning, the Internet, technology, digital, Zoom platform, information, approach.*

Higher educational establishments in Uzbekistan were partially ready to offer distance learning. A Moodle system was created on the platforms of higher education institutions, which contained electronic resources for all subjects. However, despite the fact that the system was introduced a few years ago, its implementation was slow in practice, so it was natural to face its own problems and difficulties in the introduction of emergency distance learning for the first time in the history of our country.

Distance education, also called distance learning, provides learning chances to people who could not afford time or money for traditional classes or who lived in remote areas far from schools. Because of the expansion of the Internet in recent years, the Internet has become the most important tool for delivering distance education.

With the boost of development, significant changes are taking place in the education system of our country. It is gratifying that distance learning is widely used, along with other forms of education.

It is undoubtedly known that this method has many advantages. All higher education institutions are working on the implementation of distance learning techniques and technologies. The development of information technology requires a new approach to the organization of distance learning. Modern models of distance learning are based on communication and network technologies. While these technologies provide users with a wide range of information, they also pose a challenge to their protection [2, 46].

Lack of direct communication between teacher and listener in distance learning also causes some problems. For example, there are some difficulties in organizing a problem-based learning process. Problem-based learning in the preparation of the listener as a professional can be achieved through teleconferencing. However, this does not completely solve the problem. Additional training materials will need to be developed to address this issue. These include different levels of problem-solving tasks, problem-solving instructions, and so on.

Training a specialist who fully meets modern requirements is the need of the hour. At present, a lot of positive work is being done in our country to educate, train, educate the younger generation, to approach modern information technologies and to teach them to work with new techniques and technologies. The most important of these is Distance Learning Techniques and Technology. In this regard, the steps to prepare the younger generation for distance learning can be implemented as follows:

In today's world of information technology, distance learning is becoming more and more important. Because this type of education differs from the existing ones in some respects. The difference between DL and other types of full-time education is that this type of education can involve a very wide range of people. DL has the positive features of full-time and part-time education. In this regard, DL is one of the most promising types of education today.

It is not necessary to gather a certain part of the population who wants to study at the location of the educational institution in order to provide education on the basis of DL. Second, there is no need for the listener or student to overspend. Third, the age limit for those involved in this type of education can be excluded.

There is a lack of digital literacy among teachers and students to use Internet technologies, second, low internet speeds, third, low internet access in some countries or almost non-existent for the majority of the population, and fourth, most lack of modern technologies including, computers, laptops, gadgets for distance reading. Undoubtedly, this situation has negatively affected the quality of education, technical failures and other factors have led to disruptions in the learning process. But at the same time, global experts acknowledge that the strict quarantine rules introduced due to the pandemic have created new opportunities for education, including higher education [3, 15].

The main problem is that students live in different parts of the country - in the most remote villages from the capital, the regional center, the district center, and the communication system varies from region to region. In this process, the chances of students living only in the capital, regional and district centers were a bit higher. These video lessons especially on the Zoom platform.

The multidisciplinary nature of distance learning is reflected in the principles of curriculum planning and course development. Distance education is aimed at meeting the needs of the audience, prioritizing the diversity of technologies.

The effective use of new information technologies plays an important role in the ongoing reforms in the education system of our country. The second phase of the National Training Program focuses on strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions and providing them with advanced pedagogical technologies. Therefore, a large-scale work is being carried out in higher education institutions, professional colleges and academic lyceums on the introduction of new pedagogical technologies in distance learning.

The importance of distance learning in Uzbekistan is a more active approach and a creative approach to teaching, the use of interactive methods and the widespread use of digital technologies in teaching.

The digital turn in higher education and pedagogical technologies requires the use of a variety of teaching approaches and methods. The quarantine period in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic caused the need for a radical transformation of the higher education system, its new paradigm in a modern digital society. In such conditions, it becomes necessary to form a digital educational environment and many countries, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, have faced this task.

Students need to develop skills in working with information, in particular, the use of information and communication technologies in the process of solving cognitive tasks and performing creative tasks in cognitive and educational activities.

All these processes update the topic of the article and require an analysis of the experience of using electronic educational resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The attempt to offer an analysis of the possibilities, as well as the main advantages of using electronic educational resources in teaching disciplines in higher education, using the example of Uzbekistan.

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